

777372 - RESOLUTE

Research Empowerment on Solute Carriers

**WP1 – Generation of
reagents and cell lines to
allow system-wide study of
the SLC family**

D1.4 SLC overexpressing cell lines

Lead contributors	Gernot Wolf (1 – CeMM Research Center for Molecular Medicine of the Austrian Academy of Sciences)
	Klaus Seuwen (9 - Novartis Pharma AG)
	gwolf@cemm.at, klaus.seuwen@novartis.com
Other contributors	Barbara Barbosa (1 – CeMM Research Center for Molecular Medicine of the Austrian Academy of Sciences)
	Eirini Christodoulaki (1 – CeMM Research Center for Molecular Medicine of the Austrian Academy of Sciences)
	Alvaro Ingles-Prieto (1 – CeMM Research Center for Molecular Medicine of the Austrian Academy of Sciences)
	Ulrich Goldmann (1 – CeMM Research Center for Molecular Medicine of the Austrian Academy of Sciences)
	Christoph Klimek (1 – CeMM Research Center for Molecular Medicine of the Austrian Academy of Sciences)
	Svenja Onstein (1 – CeMM Research Center for Molecular Medicine of the Austrian Academy of Sciences)
	Vitaly Sedlyarov (1 – CeMM Research Center for Molecular Medicine of the Austrian Academy of Sciences)
	Tabea Wiedmer (1 – CeMM Research Center for Molecular Medicine of the Austrian Academy of Sciences)
	Diana Santacruz (10 - Boehringer Ingelheim)
Coralie Viollet (10 - Boehringer Ingelheim)	

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Abstract

RESOLUTE aims to unlock the therapeutic potential of solute carriers (SLCs) in a systematic and coordinated effort. To reach this goal, loss- and gain-of-function studies using suitable cell models are crucial. Besides knock-out (KO) and overexpression (OE) cell lines (reported in D1.2, D1.3 and D1.5) we also aimed to provide rescuable KO cell lines in which the deleted SLC can be re-expressed (hereafter referred to as KO-OE cells). To generate these cells, we took advantage of our KO clone collection covering approximately 300 SLCs and re-introduced inducible lentiviral vectors to express codon optimized SLC cDNAs. These cDNAs contained several mutations at the gene sequence which is targeted by the gRNA expressed in the KO clone to prevent editing of the transgene. To this date, we generated KO-OE cell lines for 213 targets, cell lines for 20 more targets are currently being created. For each SLC, two KO clones were used to generate two KO-OE pools to ensure phenotypic changes in response to SLC overexpression is not limited to a particular cell clone. For quality control and cell line characterization, we performed mycoplasma and sterility testing as well as whole RNA sequencing (RNA-seq). Within the RESOLUTE consortium, these cell lines are mainly used for targeted and untargeted metabolomics and transcriptomics. We believe that, together with the corresponding WT and KO cells, these KO-OE cell lines will provide a highly valuable set of gain-of-function, loss-of-function and rescue models for RESOLUTE and the broader scientific community.

Methods

Generation of KO clones:

The generation of the KO clones used to create KO-OE cell lines is described in the report for D1.2.

Lentiviral expression vectors:

We previously generated inducible lentiviral expression vectors with C-terminal HA and Twin-Strep® tags for 447 SLCs (see deliverable D1.1). Additionally, expression vectors with Nt-tagged SLC cDNAs (with STOP codons after the SLC ORF) were generated for a subset of targets for which expression levels and/or subcellular localization were believed to be affected by the tag position. All cDNAs had been optimized for human codon usage before gene synthesis and it was ensured that the gRNAs used to generate the KO clones could not target the codon-optimized sequences.

Transduction of KO clones and transgene induction:

KO clones were transduced with viral supernatant of 293T cells transfected with the corresponding lentiviral expression vectors. After selection with Blasticidine for at least ten days, surviving clones were pooled and further expanded to prepare freeze stocks and samples for cell line characterization. Transgene expression was induced by adding 1 µg/ml Doxycycline to the growth media 24 hours before sample collection.

Quality control and multi-parameter cell line characterization:

Mycoplasma testing:

Samples were prepared according to the guidelines of the service provider (Eurofins) and were submitted for Mycoplasma testing by PCR. Furthermore, media was visually monitored for bacterial contaminations after culturing without antibiotics. We tested about 330 out of the 426 (77%) generated KO-OE cell lines and did not identify any mycoplasma contaminations.

RNA-seq:

RNA was purified from doxycycline-induced and uninduced cells at CeMM and sent for library generation and deep sequencing on a NovaSeq machine at Boehringer Ingelheim. Expression of codon-optimized cDNAs was determined by mapping reads to all generated cDNA sequences to monitor transgene induction and cross-contamination with other cDNAs that may have occurred during plasmid preparation, cell transfection or cell line propagation. All cell lines with substantial amounts of contaminating transcripts (>5% of the cDNA that is primarily expressed) were re-generated using new plasmid preparations. We tolerated cell lines with <5% of contaminating transcripts since trace amounts of cross-contaminations may occur

during RNA sample preparation in 96-well format and a small fraction of RNA-seq reads may be mapped to wrong cDNAs due to sequence similarity. Importantly, RNA-seq data showed general low levels of transgene expression before induction below 5 transcripts per million (TPM), and an approximately 30-100-fold increase in mRNA expression after induction. To further characterize these cell lines, RNA-seq data of two uninduced and two induced KO-OE pools in replicates per target were used to quantify endogenous transcripts. So far, full sets of RNA-seq data (8 samples) have been generated for 147 targets. Samples for another 65 targets have been prepared and will be sequenced shortly. Differential expression of genes was determined using DESeq2. This analysis revealed several transcriptional responses that could be clearly assigned to SLC function and allowed phenotypical clustering of several targets. We believe that these data represent a unique opportunity to systematically study the impact of the SLC transporter activity on the transcriptional profile of the cell.

Results

The generated KO-OE cell lines are intensively used for transcriptomics and metabolomics studies by the RESOLUTE consortium. Additionally, they provide valuable models to confirm assays or substitute the Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 overexpression cell lines when endogenous expression levels lead to saturation of assay readouts. We did not fully reach the desired goal of KO-OE pools for at least 300 targets yet due to two bottlenecks in generating these cell lines: First, two KO clones needed to be available to create both KO-OE pools and the final batch of KO clones was only identified recently. Second, we wanted to avoid expressing mislocalized SLCs in our KO clones and therefore relied on subcellular localization data from Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 overexpression cell lines. For many targets, these data only became available recently and in a significant number of cases it is not possible to clearly determine localization based on the imaging data. Therefore, we are currently in the process of concluding this effort with approximately 40 targets in the pipeline, which will bring us to a total of approximately 270 SLCs.

Discussion

Together with KO and WT cells, these KO-OE rescue models provide an ideal toolset to study SLC function. Re-expressing genes after genetic depletion is the gold standard to confirm functions of genes that were determined in KO models. A drawback of most overexpression models is that transgenes are expressed at levels often several magnitudes above endogenous expression levels. However, in our system transgene expression was around 3 TPM in the uninduced state and around 100-500 TPM after induction with doxycycline. Importantly, the most strongly expressed SLCs have endogenous expression levels in the latter range, indicating that our transgenes are expressed at near physiological levels for SLCs.

Another strength of these KO-OE pools is that the uninduced samples are precise controls that allow to detect even subtle changes that result from SLC overexpression. And since we generated two KO-OE pools from two independent KO clones, it is also possible to ensure that any observed changes are not restricted to a particular subclone.

Nevertheless, overexpression of tagged transgenes always bears the risk of undesired effects such as mislocalization or altered protein properties caused by the protein tag, possibly missing regulatory elements in the untranslated regions of the mRNA, or the usually moderately higher expression levels of the transgene. Unfortunately, we did not have the resources to determine subcellular localization in all our KO-OE cell lines. We therefore used subcellular localization data from our Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 overexpression cell lines as a proxy to determine whether an SLC is localized at the “natural” cellular compartment before using an overexpression construct to create KO-OE pools. However, these localization data come from a different cell line (where transgene expression levels are on average about 5-fold higher) and are therefore not necessarily reflecting the localization in our KO-OE pools. Furthermore, it is not always clear where an SLC should be located since published localization data (if available at all) might be incorrect or differ from cell type to cell type.

Conclusion

The aim to generate and characterize KO-OE cell lines for 300 SLCs will be mostly reached (expected for 90% of targets).

Repository for cell lines and primary data

All generated KO-OE cell lines will be released to the public eventually. A reagent release proposal for these cell lines is planned for summer 2022. CeMM, as owner of the cell lines, will then be responsible to distribute cell lines to interested parties after corresponding MTAs have been signed by the recipient and distributor. CeMM will only do so as long there are sufficient resources for the distribution efforts. A deposit of the KO-OE cell lines at a cell bank is not planned since it is relatively low effort to re-generate these cell lines from the KO clones deposited at ATCC (see D1.2). We are currently working on making the lentiviral vectors used to overexpress SLCs available at Addgene to allow all recipients of KO cells to re-express the SLCs themselves.

RNA-seq data will be made available to the public via the RESOLUTE web portal after the corresponding data release has been approved by the consortium partners (planned for spring 2022). RNA-seq data will in addition be deposited at the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA).

The RESOLUTE web portal will provide an overview on the KO-OE cell lines and will also allow to download sequencing results (raw data) for all experiments. Transcript and gene quantification (processed data) as well as the results of the differential expression analyses (analysed data) will be not only available for download in tabular format but can also be interactively explored via a dashboard visualization.